

ISic1664

Fragment of a Latin inscription recording building works

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

marble

Object

tablet

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory 632

Physical Description

A small fragment of a marble slab, broken on all sides, with a projecting element across the lower part, as if part of a base

Dimensions

Height 14 cm

Width 17 cm

Depth 5 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: 081506

[---]

1. sestertios \bar{C} \bar{m} (ilia) quae [rerem ? - - -]

Apparatus

Translation (en)

Translation (it)

Commentary

One of two fragments (the other is ISic3153), similar in palaeography and material, which may or may not be part of a single text (commonly edited as such), and which may or may not in turn be further fragments of the letter of Iulius Paternus (ISic0308). The fragments were considered by Mommsen and others (e.g. Manganaro 1989) to be part of the letter of Iulius Paternus of CIL 10.7024.i, published by Mommsen as 10.7024.ii and iii. However Manganaro

(1959), and more recently Korhonen (2004), consider these two frr. to be part of a separate but contextually similar inscription, recording sums of money and building works linked to the port, and so probably also by Iulius Paternus, or under him. Korhonen correctly observes that it is not necessary that the two fragments CIL 10.7024.ii (ISic3153) and iii (this one) come from a single text; hence they are published separately here. Note that Manganaro 1989 reported this, the smallest fragment (CIL 10.7024.iii) to be lost, but it has since been rediscovered in the Museo Civico.

Digital identifiers:

TM 653658

EDR 081506

Bibliography

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